

PHONETIC, PHONOLOGICAL, GRAMMATICAL, SEMANTIC,
ETYMOLOGICAL, LEXICAL AND STYLISTIC PECULIARITIES OF
ENGLISH IN COMPARISON WITH NATIVE LANGUAGE

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Annotation

This article gives information about grammar, origin, phonetics, morphology between English and Uzbek. In this article it has several paragraphs, which give full data about this. In this article, candidates can learn how to be a good learner. And candidates can learn how to use it? In this article it has several paragraphs, which give full data about this.

Key words: phonetics, tenses, suffix, grammar, origin, morphology, lexical, etymology, types of grammar

Phonetics is the study of the range of sounds which occur in speech, including the way they are produced by the speech organs and their acoustic properties. Phonology is the study of the distribution of and the relationships between speech sounds, i.e, the system of sounds of a language. Phonetics is a branch of linguistics that focuses on the production and classification of the world's speech sounds. The production of speech looks at the interaction of different vocal organs, for example the lips, tongue and teeth, to produce particular sounds. By classification of speech, we focus on the sorting of speech sounds into categories which can be seen in what is called the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). The IPA is a framework that uses a single symbol to describe each distinct sound in the language and can be found in dictionaries and in textbooks worldwide. For example, the noun 'fish' has four letters, but the IPA presents this as three sounds: f i ʃ, where 'ʃ' stands for the 'sh' sound.

Phonetics as an interdisciplinary science has many applications. This includes its use in forensic investigations when trying to work out whose voice is behind a recording. Another use is its role in language teaching and learning, either when learning a first language or when trying to learn a foreign language. This section of the

website will look at some of the branches of phonetics as well as the transcription of speech and some history behind phonetics.

Most people think of themselves as grammar rebels, seeing the rules as strict, basic and arbitrary. But grammar is actually complex, not to mention essential: Incorrect grammar can cause confusion and change the way you're perceived (or even keep you from landing a job).

That's why a grammar checker is essential if writing is part of your workday — even if that's just sending emails. Here's what else you should know about grammar:

What is grammar in English?

At a high level, the definition of grammar is a system of rules that allow us to structure sentences. It includes several aspects of the English language, like:

Parts of speech (verbs, adjectives, nouns, adverbs, prepositions, conjunctions, modifiers, etc.)

Clauses (e.g. independent, dependent, compound)

Punctuation (like commas, semicolons, and periods — when applied to usage)

Mechanics of language (like word order, semantics, and sentence structure)

Grammar's wide scope can make proofreading difficult. And the dry, academic conversations that often revolve around it can make people's eyes glaze over. But without these grammatical rules, chaos would ensue. So even if you aren't a fan (and who really is?), it's still important to understand.

Types of grammar (and theories)

As long as there have been rules of grammar, there have been theories about what makes it work and how to classify it. For example, American linguist Noam Chomsky posited the theory of universal grammar. It says that common rules dictate all language.

In his view, humans have an innate knowledge of language that informs those rules. That, he reasoned, is why children can pick up on complex grammar without explicit knowledge of the rules. But grammarians still debate about whether this theory holds true. There are also prescriptive and descriptive grammar types:

Prescriptive grammar is the set of rules people should follow when using the English language. Descriptive grammar is how we describe the way people are using language.

Semantic etymology (a word coined by Bronkhorst), as opposed to Historical etymology, attempts to elucidate the meaning of a word and gain information thence; thus, in effect, covering a deeper and wider area than historical.

Stylistics is often defined as the linguistic study of style in language. Style arises from motivated choice and choices have consequences. Stylistic analysis necessitates

both linguistic description and an assessment of the interpretative consequences of whatever choice has been made. Lexical meaning is given explicitly while stylistic meaning is always implied. Lexical meaning is relatively stable, and stylistic meaning is liable to change as it is affected by extralinguistic factors. Each language has its own grammar and origin, phonetics, morphology. When we learn a new language, we undoubtedly compare it to our mother tongue. And this thing is called cross-linguistics in science. In addition, this science gives us great opportunities for conducting research. In today's article, we will compare Uzbek and English grammar. In this we will look at the difference in the phonetics of the two languages, the differences in their origins.

If we divide our speech into small parts, the last point of division is sounds will be. For example, the sentence Uzbekistan is a paradise country Uzbekistan, paradise, to the words of the country, these words, in turn, are Oz-be-kis-ton, jan-nat-ma-kon, ol-ka to the syllables, and the syllables are like divided into sounds. It is the last point of division, which is not divided into other small pieces a speech fragment (acoustic-articulatory unit) is a sound and related events is studied in the phonetics department of linguistics.

The word phonetics is derived from the Greek word phone - "sound". In phonetics

only speech sounds are studied, not any sounds in nature. Information transfer and information reception between the speaker and the listener activity is considered speech activity. If the unit of the phonological (phonetic) level of the language is a phoneme, then the phoneme is real its pronounced, ear-heard appearance is considered background (allophone) or sound.

SOUND AND PHONEME

In linguistics, the concepts of sound and phoneme are different. In the process of speech, it is actually pronounced, the smallest we hear with our ears a piece of speech that is not divided into other small pieces is considered a sound. In direct observation, the word pronounced through several sounds and its a sequence that performs the task of forming and differentiating meaningful units.

Phoneme is the smallest unit of language that cannot be divided into smaller parts.

If the test asks for a phoneme, the sound that serves to distinguish two words from each other you will get. For example, the words stone-roof are distinguished by sh and m. So m and sh are phonemes. One phoneme is realized through several sounds. Two or more phonemes defined by contrasting meaningful units. A phoneme is a sound

that distinguishes meaning. Sounds that differentiate the meaning. A paronym is a single sound in words. In this case, the rest is the same

the arrangement of the sounds should be the same. For example: bir-pir, bayt-payt, bobbop, dor-tor, dog-tog, Hasan-Husan, knowledge-language. If the arrangement of the sounds is different, the phonemes in such words is not considered a distinguishing sound. For example: ost-sot, ust-sut Uzbek and English grammar are different. First, the structure of the sentence is completely different. English sentence structure: possessive, participle, and secondary clause. and in Uzbek: possessive, secondary participle, and participle. besides, to be (am, is, are.) is considered a verb. comes after the owner and is a possessive verb. In Uzbek, it is called a person-number suffix and always comes in the form of a verb: -man, -san, -dir, -siz, -miz. English has 12 tenses as all English learners know. its basis is 3. Uzbek language has the same form, only Uzbek language has 3 main tenses. however, like English, it also has the past, perfect, and continuous tenses. however, unlike English, it is not studied with a separate name and is studied in the main tense.

English phonetics and Uzbek phonetics are fundamentally different. we know that in English words are not read as they are written. reading has its own rule of law. they differ in the order in which vowels and consonants occur. but in Uzbek it is not like that, it is read as it is written. Uzbek phonetics studies groups of letters, such as voiced, unvoiced, front-back, short-length, and this is the main rule for correct pronunciation. Besides, their plural suffix is represented by s. but with the origin of words, they cause some exceptions, that is, in the etymology of words different from the Uzbek language. for example, there are many words in English such as person and people, woman women, mouse mice. and in Uzbek language there is no change from it.

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